

SmartCare: A Unified Machine Learning Framework for Multi-Disease Prediction

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ABSTRACT

Most of the existing machine learning models applied in healthcare can only identify a single disease, for example, diabetes, heart disease, or lung disease. This is a major drawback, necessitating patients and healthcare professionals to utilize several platforms for an integrated diagnosis, which can lead to inefficiencies and delays in treatment. Machine learning, being a branch of artificial intelligence, has demonstrated great potential in automating diagnosis by studying patterns in large datasets and making precise predictions. Building on this potential, our project presents a single, machine-learning-based prediction system that can diagnose a variety of diseases within a single platform. The model in question employs proven classification algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Logistic Regression, which are trained and tested with publicly available health datasets obtained from Kaggle. Python libraries that are fundamental for data manipulation include Pandas and NumPy, while Scikit-learn is utilized for building and testing models. The models are serialized by Pickle and incorporated into a web interface developed using Streamlit. Such a system not only increases end-user accessibility but also minimizes diagnosis time while keeping it highly accurate. It is a useful digital health tool for early disease diagnosis, real-time health monitoring, and deployment on a large scale in clinical or remote environments.

Keywords: Digital Health, Real-time Prediction, Symptoms, Data-Driven, Healthcare, Disease Prediction, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression, Machine Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of machine learning (ML) methods in the health sector has proven to be very promising in terms of improving diagnostic accuracy and efficiency. ML models can analyze complicated data-driven predictions, making them great assets for the early detection of diseases and patient

monitoring.[3] Yet most current ML-based diagnostic frameworks are only for the prediction of one disease or another, such as diabetes, heart disease, and parkinsons disease. This incompleteness constitutes a significant constraint, as individuals and clinicians end up using many platforms for

Overall evaluation. It can result in inefficiencies, delayed diagnosis, and poor outcomes for patients.

Machine learning, being a subset of artificial intelligence, provides powerful tools for building predictive models via supervised learning algorithms. With large amounts of healthcare data, it is possible to build models that generalize across more than one disease type. This paper introduces an integrated prediction system that combines the classification power of several machine learning models into a single, usable platform.[15]

The system suggested uses classification models like Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Logistic Regression, which are trained and tested on publicly available medical data obtained from Kaggle. Python libraries like Pandas and NumPy are employed to preprocess and manipulate the data, whereas Scikit-learn is the main framework used for model training and model validation. The models that are trained are Pickled and hosted using an interactive web application developed with the Streamlit library.

This combined system increases diagnostic convenience, minimizes processing time, and keeps high prediction performance. It is a scalable digital health platform that can be applied in both clinical and remote settings, enabling real-time monitoring of health and the early detection of diseases.

Machine learning presents a revolutionary solution by facilitating timely and accurate diagnosis of diseases from patient symptoms and clinical information. Specifically, ML-driven multi-disease prediction models are picking up steam with the ability to deliver personalized diagnoses, facilitate timely interventions, and suggest targeted interventions.

A number of challenges confront such systems despite their potential, including the requirement for large, diverse, and representative datasets; the possibility of algorithmic bias; and the need to ensure ethical, transparent deployment. [2]

The area of multi-disease prediction with ML is developing very quickly. With more healthcare information becoming accessible and technological capabilities increasing, ML algorithms will become more precise, resilient, and trustworthy, future enhancing healthcare provision. Classification-based ML models like Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine (SVM) are commonly applied in medical diagnosis because they have high predictive performance and interpretability.[3]

In addition, machine learning has seen extensive use in a variety of fields, ranging from marketing and scientific study to particularly medical diagnosis. Classification is one of the ML methods that serves a crucial purpose in healthcare by facilitating patient data categorization and disease existence or progression prediction. With ongoing enhancements in ML models and data availability, intelligent systems can potentially significantly improve medical diagnosis and healthcare efficiency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of machine learning in predicting various diseases, with Parkinson's, cancer, mental health conditions, and diabetes being notable areas of focus. In the study title "Diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease using Artificial neural Network" by Anila M. et al[21], the authors explored the potential of speech analysis in diagnosing Parkinson's disease. Several machine learning algorithms, including

Artificial Neural Network(ANN), Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors(KNN), Support Vector Machine(SVM), and XGBoost, were tested. Although the ANN model with two hidden layers showed promising results, the study's limitation was its restricted architecture, which did not explore deeper neural networks or advanced feature selection methods that could potentially enhance accuracy.[5],[6]

Support Vector Machine(SVM) has merged as a widely used algorithm for illness prediction based on patient symptoms. Implemented SVM for symptom-based classification of diseases, finding it to be effective despite its relatively longer computation time. Additionally, cancer prediction has been significantly enhanced through machine learning approaches that analyze clinical data, histological images, and genetic markers. These methods facilitate early diagnosis, tumor classification, and prognosis estimation.[16]

In infectious disease surveillance, ML models are also used to forecast outbreaks and monitor disease transmission based on a blend of epidemiological information and real-time feedback such as social media popularity. For mental health forecasting, ML algorithms have been used to analyze patient survey data, wearable sensor data, and text-based analysis to identify anxiety and depression conditions.[6]

A number of studies have also discussed the significance of ethics and privacy in using machine learning in health care. With these models becoming increasingly dependent on sensitive personal information, issues of algorithm bias, explainability, and adherence to ethical requirements have come into the foreground.

III. METHODOLOGY

The approach taken in this research is the design and implementation of a single machine learning-based system for the prediction of multiple diseases at once. The system is built based on an extensive dataset of patient records for different chronic diseases. The dataset is thoroughly preprocessed, involving missing value handling, normalization, and feature selection, to provide high-quality input for training machine learning models.

Several classification algorithms are used to compare and assess performance. They are Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Naïve Bayes, and AdaBoost. The choice of models is based on their established accuracy, generalization, and performance on medical data. Each model is trained and tested with stratified k-fold cross-validation to provide a stable evaluation and prevent overfitting. Regularization methods are also used where possible to increase model generalizability to unseen data.

Another goal of the system proposed here is to reduce the requirements for disease-specific models through facilitating multi-disease prediction through one interface. This method increases efficiency and convenience by enabling clinicians to diagnose several conditions without the need to alternate between individual models.

All models are created with the programming language Python and utilize libraries like Pandas, Numpy, Scikit-learn, and Pickle for data processing, model training, and serialization. The end product is deployed with the Streamlit framework, presenting a user-friendly and interactive user interface.

Figure 1: The System Architecture

Figure 2: The Sequence Diagram

System architecture is a high-level conceptual model that specifies the structure, behavior, and critical elements of a system. It gives a formalized description aimed at improving understanding of the system's operation and design. This architectural framework, as shown in Figure 1, is normally made up of several subsystems and components that communicate.

Sequence diagrams, or event diagrams, event scenarios, are critical to making the shift from high-level system requirements, which are normally described in use cases, to lower-level, more formal system designs. Sequence diagrams assist in the visualization of the dynamic nature of the system by showing the sequence of the interactions among system components and outside parties. As shown in Figure 2, the sequence diagram of the prediction system describes the interaction process in which the system first gathers input data from the user (actor) and saves it in a dataset. Then, the system processes the training data, retrieves relevant information from the dataset, and uses machine learning (ML) algorithms on training and testing data. The system then compares the user's input status with the ground truth status to produce a predictive output.

Figure 3: The Deployment Diagram

Deploy software components onto the physical design. As a link between software design and its execution environment, deployment diagrams graphically show how the system will operate in real hardware environments, where a node is a particular computational unit or device.

IV. DATASETS AND PREPROCESSING

Implementation is the actualization of a technical specification or technique as an operational system by programming and deployment. In software engineering, this is the process of translating conceptual models into executable code, modules, or full software applications.

The process of the suggested multi-disease prediction system starts with choosing suitable datasets for training and testing. The datasets are composed of different attributes—age, gender, and heart rate—representing major prediction features. Careful preprocessing of data is crucial to make machine learning algorithms function effectively.

For the purposes of improving predictive performance and interpretability of the model, categorical attributes are converted into binary forms (e.g., “0” and “1”) in order to support compatibility with used algorithms. Additionally, dealing with imbalanced datasets is an essential step towards building strong models. This research uses both oversampling and undersampling methods. Undersampling reduces the majority class to balance the dataset and is used when sufficient data is available. Oversampling, however, adds more samples of the minority class to bring about balance, thereby enhancing model performance on underrepresented classes.

4.1 Parkinson’s Disease Prediction

The Parkinson Disease prediction module is one of the core of a multiple Disease prediction system. It uses data about the Effected and normal people data preferences to generate the result of the patient [14]. It performs the Different machine algorithms likeKNN, XGBoost, SVM, RANDOM FOREST, etc

4.1.1 Attribute Information

1. Name: Recording number and ASCII topic name.
2. MDVP: Fo(Hz): Vocal Fundamental Average (in Hz).
3. MDVP: Flo(Hz): Minimum Vocal Fundamental frequency of the voice.
4. MDVP: Flo(Hz): Minimum Vocal Fundamental Frequency (in Hz).
5. Jitter Metrics:
 MDVP: Jitter(%): Percentage of fundamental frequency variation.
 MDVP: Jitter(Abs): Absolute jitter value.
 MDVP: RAP: Relative amplitude perturbation.
 MDVP: PPQ: Five-point period perturbation quotient.
 Jitter: DDP: Derivative of amplitude perturbation.
6. Shimmer Metrics:
 MDVP: Shimmer: Amplitude variation.
 MDVP: Shimmer(dB): Shimmer in dB.
 Shimmer: APQ3: Three-point amplitude perturbation quotient. Shimmer: APQ5: Five-point amplitude perturbation quotient. MDVP: APQ: Eleven-point amplitude perturbation quotient. Shimmer: DDA: Difference in amplitude perturbation.
7. NHR and HNR: Measurements of the voice's noise to-tone component ratio.

4.1.2 Classification Report

8. status: Subject's health status, categorized as (0) for healthy or (1) for Parkinson's.
9. Nonlinear Dynamical Complexity Metrics:
 RPD: Nonlinear measurement of underlying frequency change. D2: Nonlinear dynamical complexity metric.
10. DFA: Exponent of signal fractal scaling.
11. Nonlinear Frequency Change Metrics:
 spread1: Spread of nonlinear measures of fundamental frequency change.
 spread2: Spread of nonlinear measures of fundamental frequency change.
 PPE: Pitch period entropy.
 Comparison of Models.

4.2.2 Comparison of Models

	Model Name	Train Accuracy(%)	Test Accuracy(%)	AUC Score
0	Logistic Regression	82.524272	74.576271	0.887879
1	Decision Tree Classifier	83.980583	88.135593	0.910606
2	AdaBoost	83.980583	88.135593	0.854545
3	Random Forest Classifier	99.029126	84.745763	0.841667
4	kNN	100.000000	98.305085	0.966667
5	SVM	100.000000	94.915254	0.992424
6	XGBoost	100.000000	91.525424	0.956061

We can say that KNN Model is good for our dataset but SVM giving more AUC.

```
knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=1)
knn.fit(X_train, y_train)

y_pred_knn = knn.predict(X_test)

print(knn.score(X_train, y_train))
print(knn.score(X_test, y_test))

print(metrics.classification_report(y_test, y_pred_knn))
```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.00	0.93	0.97	15
1	0.98	1.00	0.99	44
accuracy			0.98	59
macro avg	0.99	0.97	0.98	59
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	59

4.2 Diabetes Disease Prediction

Using several supervised machine learning techniques, the prediction seeks to identify a patient's likelihood of developing diabetes early on. It uses data about the Effected and normal people data preferences to generate Whether person is affected or not from a particular Disease.

4.2.1 Attribute information

1. Pregnancies
2. Glucose
3. Blood pressure
4. Skin Thickness
5. Insulin
6. BMI
7. Diabetes Pedigree Function
8. Age

4.2.2 Comparison of Models

```
# Accuracy on test set
print("Logistic Regression: " + str(accuracy_logreg * 100))
print("K Nearest neighbors: " + str(accuracy_knn * 100))
print("Support Vector Classifier: " + str(accuracy_svc * 100))
print("Naive Bayes: " + str(accuracy_nb * 100))
print("Decision tree: " + str(accuracy_dectree * 100))
print("Random Forest: " + str(accuracy_ranfor * 100))
```

Logistic Regression: 71.42857142857143
 K Nearest neighbors: 78.57142857142857
 Support Vector Classifier: 73.37662337662337
 Naive Bayes: 71.42857142857143
 Decision tree: 68.18181818181817
 Random Forest: 75.97402597402598

4.2.3 Classification Report

```
# Classification report
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report
print(classification_report(Y_test, Y_pred_knn))
```

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.0	0.81	0.87	100
1	1.0	0.72	0.63	54
micro avg	0.79	0.79	0.79	154
macro avg	0.77	0.75	0.76	154
weighted avg	0.78	0.79	0.78	154

4.3 Heart Disease Prediction

It uses data about the Effected and normal people data preferences to generate the result of the patient [37]. It performs the Different machine algorithms like KNN, XGBoost, SVM, RANDOM FOREST, etc. This seeks to forecast using various supervised machine learning techniques.

4.3.1 Attribute information

1. Age
2. Sexual
3. Types of Chest Pain
4. Blood pressure at rest
5. Cholesterol serum
6. Blood sugar fasting
7. Resting Heart diagram Outcome
8. Peak heart rate attained
9. Workout Lessened Angina
10. Fluorescene-colored vessels

4.3.2 Accuracy Results

V. RESULT

The results of the designed system illustrate that it can predict diseases earlier, accurately, and reliably compared to current methodologies. Different machine learning algorithms have been utilized to obtain maximum results. Once a user has entered the pertinent parameters for a given disease, the system checks if the subject is inclined to get affected by the disease or not. Every parameter provides a valid range. If a value supplied by the user is out of this range, invalid, or left blank, the system will show a warning message to enter a valid value. This is done to maintain data integrity and enhance the precision of predictions by checking inputs before processing.

5.1 Parkinson's Disease Prediction

Figure 4: Parkinson's Disease Prediction Home Page

Figure 5: Parkinson's Disease Prediction Result

5.2 Heart Disease Prediction

Figure 6: The Heart Disease Prediction Home Page

Figure 7: Heart Disease Prediction Result

5.3 Diabetes Prediction

Figure 8: Diabetes Prediction Home Page

Figure 9: Diabetes Prediction Result Page

VI. CONCLUSION

In the modern age, because of lifestyle and conditions of the environment, people have become more and more prone to a variety of diseases. An early diagnosis and prediction are really important to help prevent many diseases from advancing into advanced stages. But it's not easy to diagnose diseases by hand accurately in many cases by doctors.

Machine learning (ML)-driven multi-disease prediction represents a highly promising leap forward in the world of medicine, with the potential to revolutionize the way

diseases are diagnosed and managed. Through the analysis of large volumes of patient data, ML algorithms have the ability to identify subtle patterns and interdependencies not necessarily apparent to human physicians. This can enable earlier diagnosis, more targeted treatment regimens, and dramatically enhanced patient outcomes.

Although promising, bringing ML to healthcare is not without challenges—most notably, the possibility of algorithmic bias

and the need for diverse, representative data. Emerging research and development are attempting to work through these limitations, incrementally unlocking ML's full potential for disease prediction.

With greater technology and availability of data, ML algorithms are likely to be more advanced and precise. With this evolution, there will be more customized treatments and improved health outcomes. Eventually, the application of machine learning for the prediction of multiple diseases is a thrilling and revolutionary future of healthcare.

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